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PLASMA-SURFACE INTERACTIONS IN CO₂ GLOW DISCHARGES

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Heterogeneous surface kinetics plays an important role in most plasma processes, where surfaces interact either with active discharges or their afterglows. In plasmas for CO₂ conversion, adsorption and recombination of atomic oxygen on reactor surfaces determine the gas composition and the availability of O for dissociation and recombination reactions ($\text{CO}_2 + \text{O} \rightarrow \text{CO} + \text{O}_2$; $\text{CO} + \text{O} + \text{M} \rightarrow \text{CO}_2 + \text{M}$). Measurements in the positive column of oxygen-containing glow discharges in a Pyrex tube of 10 mm inner radius, for wall temperatures between -20°C and 50°C (50°C in the figure), highlighted that the loss frequencies of O (ν_{loss}) and estimated wall recombination probabilities are significantly lower in CO₂ plasmas than in O₂ plasmas [1]. Although O recombination in O₂ plasma was recently described [2,3], the difference with respect to CO₂ plasma is poorly understood. Here we employ global modelling with surface kinetics to describe O loss in CO₂ plasmas and highlight the relevant mechanisms [4,5]. The newly developed model describes the experimental dependence of the atomic oxygen loss frequency on pressure, current, gas temperature and wall temperature and allows to identify the most important recombination mechanisms. The results suggest that partial CO passivation of chemisorption sites can justify the lower recombination in CO₂ than O₂. Moreover, the simulations highlight that source and loss volume processes are non-negligible in the analysis of O loss frequency. Figure 1 shows that the simulated O loss frequency follows the trend from experiment and highlights the contributions of the major surface recombination processes to the O loss frequency.

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